

they properly outline the situation of Jews in Italy before the occupation of northern Italy and Rome by the Nazi army in 1943 who were living isolated and in economic and social tragic conditions. The foreign Jews who had failed to emigrate were interned in local concentration camps. However, the deportation of Italian Jews to the eastern lagers would have started only after the 8th of September 1943 when the Italian interim government, led by Pietro Badoglio, signed the armistice with the Allies. Jews' condition got worse after Mussolini was released from imprisonment on the Gran Sasso, the creation of Italian Social Republic and the Nazi occupation.

The documents of the Archivio Storico Diocesano of Milan allow us to better understand the role of the Church in the assistance before fall 1943; they show the existence of a dense assistance network whose branches changed according to the kind of request. On the one hand, the assistance provided by the Curia of Milan cannot be fully understood without considering its cooperation with the Vatican; on the other hand, however, the humanitarian action carried out by the Pope and his entourage could not have been realized without all the nodes of the network.

The fuel of this network was represented by institutional and personal relationships between the members of the Court of Rome and the local clergy. Each node played an essential role without which the network as a whole could not have worked efficiently.

In the last decades historians had partially reconstructed the role of the Holy See in the Second World War scenario, and its attitude towards persecuted Jews thanks to the materials stored in the archives of the Ministry of Foreign Affairs of those nations which had relations with the Holy See and to the *Actes et documents du Saint Siège relatifs à la Seconde Guerre Mondiale*, an eleven-volume collection of documents from the Vatican historical archives published between 1965 and 1981. In 2020 Pope Francis decided to open for public access the documents of Pius XII's pontificate. This choice let the researchers understand better some contentious aspects of Pius XII's papacy. Since 2022 some studies have been published (Kertzer 2022; Riccardi 2022; Santos 2022; Valbousquet 2022) which already showed the richness and importance of those documents which are crucial to explain Pius XII's diplomatic line and the humanitarian work of the Church during the Second World War.

The assistance provided by Italian bishops to those who were persecuted for racial reasons was partially reconstructed too. The assistance offered to Jews in Rome and the cooperation between the bishop of Florence, Elia Dalla Costa, and DELASEM, a Jewish assistance organization, have already been investigated (Cavarocchi and Mazzini 2018; Riccardi 2008). However, what happened in the northern part of Italy has not been studied yet, except for the activity of archbishop Pietro Boetto in Genoa, and, in particular, what was done by archbishop Schuster to help Jews is almost unknown. In this work we aim at reconstructing the assistance network organized in Milan, the biggest diocese in Europe, and the relations between the local clergy, the Holy See and its representatives around Europe. The application of network analysis to these studies allows us to examine these documents in a different way, considering both the nodes and edges and the structure of the network. The graphic representation realised with Gephi well shows the complexity of Church's assistance net, the relationships between the representatives of the Pope and those of the Italian or foreign governments such as ambassadors and consuls. It is also evident the key role played by Schuster which is involved in the management of all the dossiers. A great advantage provided by this approach is also the possibility of analysing how the number of each kind of request evolved between 1938 and 1943. Most of the requests (233) were finalized to get the chance to expatriate to Brazil, thanks to the three thousand visas devoted to converted Jews, granted by Getulio Vargas upon the request of the Holy See. There are also several requests aimed at obtaining the "discriminazione" or a revision of the racial position. The actors involved changed according to the type of request, with the exception of the Holy See and of the Curia of Milan which were always directly engaged. The network analysis could properly be applied to describe also the assistance networks organized in other areas of the peninsula. Comparing these networks to each other, identifying both constancies and differences, could be very interesting and useful as well.

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